

Wave with Self-Spacetime Creating Notion of Average Particle in Wave-Particle Duality?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 2, 2022

A quantum particle is often described as exhibiting dual particle-wave nature. A particle seems to be an object which obeys Newton's laws/special relativity with a wave also being a phenomenon existing in Newtonian mechanics (special relativity). In other words the particle and wave are governed by x - t external variables which have infinite resolution. It was originally thought that x and t in addition to being external were absolute, but special relativity changed this idea.

We have suggested in previous notes that a free quantum particle with energy E and momentum p creates its own space time i.e time intervals are proportional to $1/E$ and space to $1/p$. This means no external clock is needed and different internal rulers and clocks exist for different E, p . It also suggests finite time and space intervals. In fact, an absolute is introduced namely $A=0 = -Et+px$ with t and x being independent. This suggests that $t \rightarrow b/E$ and $x \rightarrow b/p$. A is the free particle Lagrangian (both relativistic and nonrelativistic) with x and t being considered independent. Thus we suggest that the external x ruler and t clock of Newtonian mechanics represent an average of the internal picture and are also described by A , but with $x/t=v$ and not x and t being treated as independent. In (1) we showed that having discrete x spacing with a running time (i.e. Newton's time variable) and insisting on spatial invariance leads to dA/dx partial = p .

Thus instead of considering particle wave duality we suggest an underlying wave structure which creates its own spacetime intervals ($1/E, 1/p$), but may be mapped in certain situations to the external running x and t of Newton's theory. For example, consider an electron (a quantum particle) with a fixed p moving over a distance much greater than its wavelength. It may be mapped to Newton's external running x, t values with $x=vt$, but this is an average mapping into continuous x and t . In reality the situation is more complicated because there may be a Bohm-Aharonov effect occurring. Thus the underlying wave picture is in fact physically important and linked to interactions. Thus a self-ruler is not simply a measuring device - interactions may occur unlike in the case of the external ruler.

Given that p defines a kind of spatial invariance approximated by a periodic function $\exp(ipx)$ (eigenfunction of $-i\hbar/dx$) and that Newton's running time is not needed in a quantum bound state equilibrium, one may wonder what one should do in the case of a particle bound in a $V(x)$ potential. In Newtonian mechanics $V(x)$ suggests non-spatial invariance and $v(x)$ velocity changes with x as well in contrast with $\exp(ipx)$ which is periodically invariant. In fact Newtonian mechanics (and Lagrangian/Hamiltonian as well) focus on d/dt i.e $x(t)$. We have argued above that time intervals $1/E$ are independent of $1/p$ spatial ones. It may be noticed, however, that different p values lead to different wavelengths and so even though there is a kind of spatial invariance for each, when compared to each other this invariance is broken and superpositions of $\exp(ipx)$ may create local x probability densities. At the same they create spatial momentum densities because $-\hbar/dx (d/dx) 1/2m$ yields a kind of average kinetic energy when normalized. This seems to describe the x - p uncertainty relationship. In order to create spatial resolution (other than the built-in one in the wavelength) one needs to superpose different momenta, each

of which are spatially invariant according to their periodic scheme $\exp(ipx)$. Thus one may create an average $1/2m \langle pp \rangle$ and obtain a v_{rms} . This may be described in terms of Newtonian external running x and t variables which have infinite resolution, but this v_{rms} does not map to a physical state i.e. to $\exp(i(mv_{rms})x)$ localized at x . Rather the various $\exp(ipx)$'s which create v_{rms} are the physical entities as may be seen by knocking a particle out of a bound state. The physical $\exp(ipx)$ momenta states have spatial invariance and so cannot be associated with a specific position in space. Only their superposition creates the notion of specific position in space, but then there is a distribution of p . This seems to be the basis for the x - p uncertainty principle.

Thus we suggest that the particle of particle-wave duality is created through a mapping of a physical wave scenario to a continuous (infinite resolution) x - t scheme which in reality is an abstraction because each p, E free particle state has its own internal clock-ruler i.e. $1/E$ and $1/p$ time and space units. Given that $1/E$ and $1/p$ have finite values the idea of dt and dx tending to 0 only makes sense as an abstraction which only holds in certain situations.

External Spacetime

The idea of external spacetime seems to be natural i.e. one has a physical ruler and a clock on the wall which are used to describe dynamical processes in the macroscopic world. It was once thought that the ruler and clock were absolute i.e. would be the same in a moving frame, but special relativity changed that notion. In this picture one may control the resolution of the ruler and clock with infinite resolution for both being the ideal.

We argued in (1) that special relativity which changed the idea of absolute clocks and rulers may also be responsible for the notion of internal clocks and rulers i.e. frequencies and wavelengths which are found in light and also in particles with rest mass. We suggested that the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ (which is the nonrelativistic/relativistic free particle action with x and t being independent) suggests an absolute constant $A=0$ such that $t \rightarrow 1/E$ and $p \rightarrow 1/p$. In other words a particle has its own clock and ruler with resolutions depending on E and p . This leads to a global or absolute notion of constant speed/momentum namely $A=0$ which also holds for light. (In the case of light $E=pc$ as well, but this does not hold for a particle with rest mass.)

Furthermore we argue that a discrete x - t resolution scheme may be mapped to the continuous one used in Newtonian mechanics under certain circumstances. This we argue is the notion of particle wave - duality. We argue that the so-called wave (discrete space with $1/p$ proportional wavelengths and $1/E$ proportional time intervals) is mapped to a continuous set of variable x, t to create the notion of a particle represented by a point moving smoothly. It is no surprise that A , the classical free particle action, yields both the discrete self-spacetime and describes motion in the mapped continuous x - t world of Newton because these are one and the same if the mapping holds.

There are cases where the mapping leads to problems. For example the mapping would not predict the Bohm-Aharonov effect nor would it predict diffraction or interference from slits separated by about a wavelength. Thus the wave picture seems to be the underlying physical one. Nevertheless a mapping to the continuous x - t scenario may be made if one wishes to describe some average properties occurring over distances much longer than a wavelength in scenarios in which the wavelength is not shifted or interference introduced. In such a case one

may use external rulers and clocks. For example an electron with a wavelength and frequency follows $x=vt$ when traveling over a large distance. In such a case the mapping is good enough. In fact, in defining $\exp(ipx)$ one has to use an external ruler to make sense of x , but physically \hbar/p is the measuring device.

Free Particle Classical Action and Space and Time on the Same Footing

We examine briefly the nonrelativistic free particle action $= \int \dot{x} m v dt = \int m \dot{x} dx$. This is equivalent to $-Et+px$ i.e. $-\frac{1}{2}m\dot{x}^2 t + m\dot{x}x = -\frac{1}{2}m\dot{x}^2 t$ if $v=x/t$. One may note that E and p contain v implicitly which in turn is x/t , but E and p are treated as constants of motion in $-Et+px$. The free x and t puts x and t on the same footing for a free particle as both are dimensions in spacetime (and have resolutions). The form $-Et+px$ thus allows one to analyse the resolutions of t and x without worrying about $x=vt$ i.e. allows one to treat x and t independently except for the fact that overall $A=0$ when determining these resolutions. $-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant so using an absolute $A=0$ ensures a consistent approach to finding time and space resolutions in various frames moving at constant velocity. One might ask why spatial invariance is linked with p and not v . In (1) we argued that p appears in special relativity. The reason it appears is that mass is part of the relevant physical information and so one is not simply interested in the motion of the center of mass of an object without knowing its mass. It is momentum which is physically relevant to impulse hits. There is an average velocity associated with a particle regardless of its mass and this describes how it moves in Newton's continuous $x-t$, but does not describe the wave aberration it makes related to the self-spatial and time resolutions which are linked to momentum and energy. These are linked to interactions in addition to impulses e.g. Bohm Aharonov effect and two slit interference. Thus a wavelength of $1/p$ seems appropriate when this is associated with interactions.

One may note that if a particle with p, E has a fixed time interval proportional to $1/E$ and a space one proportional to $1/p$ then the notion of $dx \rightarrow 0$ and $dt \rightarrow 0$ does not hold. These internal spacetime resolutions may be large compared to lengths or times in a system which is the case in quantum mechanics (at least for space). One may note that the resolutions are linked to $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ which are eigenfunctions of $i\partial/\partial t \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt)$ and $-i\partial/\partial x \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$.

Spatial and Momentum Distributions Dependent on x

The idea of a built-in spacetime leads to $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ wavelike forms, but these represent a kind of periodic spatial and time invariance. What if such an invariance does not exist in a problem. For example a Newtonian bound state with potential $V(x)$ has $v(x)$ (velocity). This $v(x)$ does not map to $\exp(ipx)$ where $p=mv$ as $\exp(ipx)$ suggests spatial invariance. Nevertheless there is a spatial kinetic energy distribution $\frac{1}{2}mv(x)v(x)$ and $V(x)$ also imparts a potential energy distribution in space. These are physical notions even though they are described using Newton's external infinite resolution $x-t$ values. How does one create such spatial distributions from a scenario of free particle $\exp(ipx)$'s which are linked to spatial invariance?

We argue that even though a given $\exp(ipx)$ suggests a kind of periodic spatial invariance, different $\exp(ipx)$ s have different wavelengths and so relative to each other one does not have spatial invariance. Like with Fourier analysis, periodic spatial invariance of different wavelengths may be used to create a spatial distribution i.e. the notion of being at one x versus another. In this case, however, each $\exp(ipx)$ physically represents a momentum p so a spatial distribution immediately implies a kinetic energy (and momentum or one with any other powers of p) in x . Thus instead of using time as in Newtonian (Lagrangian/Hamiltonian) theory to differentiate different x points, one may use various free $\exp(ipx)$ s to build a linked spatial probability-momentum/kinetic spatial profile. Time i.e. external time does not appear in such a scenario (i.e. in the time-independent Schrodinger equation). It should be noted, however, that an external clock does not necessarily disappear, neither does an external ruler. It is just that it is not needed to develop a theory of interaction of a particle which has its own internal clock and ruler. This internal ruler and clock imply a physical distribution (e.g. a spatial one for momentum i.e. wavelength) which is then linked to interactions. Thus the idea of an internal ruler or wavelength is much more than simply a measuring device - it is involved in interactions which cannot be described by mapping to a continuous x - t . In particular, one may have velocity remain constant and have a phase shift as in the Bohm-Aharonov effect.

Thus an average kinetic energy:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} \text{ where } W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((1))$$

arises. This is equivalent to $.5m v_{rms}(x)v_{rms}(x)$. The interfering wave scenario with each wave containing its own spacetime intervals leads to a kinetic energy which may be described in terms of v_{rms} which may be described in terms of Newton's external continuous (infinite resolution) x - t variables. Thus the quantum waves create a kind of average particle.

One, however, does not have $\exp(i m v_{rms}(x) x)$. Rather the physical entities are the $\exp(ipx)$ s as may be seen if a particle is knocked out of a bound state. (Note- in a sense there is an external ruler present because x in $\exp(ipx)$ must be measured, but this is a mathematical variable. Physically the wavelength is measured through an interaction.)

Momentum Conservation With and Without Invariance

The eigenfunction $\exp(ipx)$ of $-i\hbar/dx$ is linked to invariance in space which in turn is linked to conservation of momentum, just as in the case of light (e.g. refraction). This leads to two kinds of interactions, impulse hits which change p to p_1 (just as reflection from a moving mirror or refraction can change p of light). A second interaction arises when p does not change, but a phase shift is picked in the Bohm Aharonov case, or an interference pattern occurs due to slits etc although the direction of p may change. The eigenfunctions $\exp(ipx)$ are orthogonal over all x so: $\int \exp(-ip_2x)\exp(-ip_3x) \exp(ip_1x) \exp(ip_2x) dx$ is nonzero only if $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$. $\exp(ipx)$ is also an eigenfunction of a_{energy} if one has a constant potential. In (1) it was shown how for a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s one could have various $\exp(ipx)$ s combine with $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$ to create a constant potential for each $\exp(ipx)$ such that the same E_n (energy) arose.

Introducing $V(x)$ leads to a breaking of spatial invariance. It was noted that taking a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s may also break spatial invariance due to a lack of relative spatial invariance between different $\exp(ipx)$ s. A linear superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s normalized leads to a spatial function so that choosing the correct constants as in ((1)) so that:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W + V(x) = E_n$$

leads to conservation of energy at each x . This in turn leads to a $p_{rms}(x)$ which due to the averaging process is not equal to:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} W(x) / W(x) \quad ((2))$$

Even for a particle in an infinite well breaking spatial invariance leads to a correct classical energy:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \sin(kx) / \sin(kx) = k^2/2m \quad ((3))$$

,but to a strange momentum: $-i \frac{d}{dx} m \sin(kx) / \sin(kx) = -i m k \cos(kx) / \sin(kx) \quad ((4))$

Classically one would have $k^2/2m$.

Thus mapping a superposition of waves without using time to Newton's continuous $t-x$ variables to create the notion of a particle only holds if one uses $p_{rms}(x)$ to represent the momentum of the particle. In such a case momentum conservation does not follow from spatial invariance as in the case of $\exp(ipx)$ and all wave notions are lost (including their interactions). Instead one has:

$dp/dt = \text{Force}(x)$ so that for equal and opposite reactions $dp_1/dt = F$ and $dp_2/dt = -F$ so:

$$d/dt (p_1+p_2) = F-F = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad p_1+p_2 = \text{constant} \quad ((5))$$

Thus one does not need to introduce invariance in the Newtonian picture to have momentum conservation, yet thinking in terms of spatial invariance leads to both momentum conservation and a wavelength which leads to new types of interactions i.e. wave-like interactions and phase shifts etc.

To see how the wave superposition picture leads to problems when it comes to momentum one may consider the Newtonian picture. In a tiny region $dx \rightarrow 0$ $v(x)$ is considered to be constant even though the particle accelerates. The acceleration is considered to be a small correction. With wavelengths of different sizes within a superposition sum there is no standard dx length. One mixes differently calibrated rulers to create a kind of spatial, momentum, kinetic energy (or higher p powers) function which depends on a continuous x . One needs to impose conservation of energy if energy is not being lost, but this may lead to problems with other powers of p especially momentum. The Newtonian picture of a changing p , however, is compatible with energy conservation and so moving from momenta due to spatial invariance in $\exp(ipx)$ to

$\text{prms}(x)$ does not violate conservation of energy which has been applied to \sum over p
 $a(p)\exp(ipx) = W(x)=\text{wavefunction}$. Nevertheless one needs to keep in mind this issue.

Newton's Approach and the Macroscopic World

We have suggested above that quantum waves create the notion of a particle. In the macroscopic world, however, one does not see waves associated with a particle and the "notion of particle" seems to be reality. We argue that in the macroscopic world the quantum frequency and wavelength are tiny, much smaller than the intervals of any ruler or external clock or lengths and times in a problem. Furthermore the form $\exp(ipx)$ represents probability. It does not mean that a particle exists simultaneously throughout space. There is only the uncertainty of it being within a wavelength or so and if this wavelength is tiny, the $\exp(ipx)$ particle is a sense like a point. Thus the Newtonian picture with continuous $x-t$ ignoring the notion of wavelength and only including conservation of energy seems to fit experimental data which cannot resolve wave related phenomena. (It is suggested in the literature that very sensitive measurements may detect quantum motion in objects as large as 70 kg, but these are somewhat new results.)

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that Newtonian mechanics/special relativity uses external rulers and clocks with ideally infinitesimal resolution. Using the idea of conservation of energy one may describe dynamics of a particle within this continuous $x-t$ picture. Special relativity, however, which rules out the idea of an absolute clock or ruler also seems to point to particles (both with and without rest mass) having internal rulers and clocks. If one writes the free particle action with $v=x/t$ such that x and t are both linear (i.e. on the same footing) one obtains $A=-Et+px$. Introducing an absolute condition $A=0$ yields t intervals proportional to $1/E$ and spatial one proportional to $1/p$. This suggests a kind of spatial and, independently, time invariance associated with a free particle (in a probabilistic view). For example considering space, one may ignore time in a probabilistic view and consider $\exp(ipx)$ which is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar/dx$. Given that the wavelength proportional to $1/p$ may take up a considerable length compared to lengths in the system, the idea of a continuous $x-t$ seems to only be an average which ignores an important physical distribution $\cos(px)$ and $i \sin(px)$ involved in certain interactions. We note that wavelength is associated with p which means that particles with different masses and speeds may have the same p . P is linked to impulse (i.e. interaction) and so is wavelength e.g. Bohm Aharonov effect and interference/diffraction and so p and not v is the link.

If one wishes to retain conservation of energy at each x point i.e use a potential $V(x)$ then one must deal with localized "average" or rms velocity and distribution. $\exp(ipx)$ for a given p represents a periodic type of spatial invariance which is not consistent with $V(x)$. Thus one needs to have the superposition of many $\exp(ipx)$ s to create spatial localization because the different periodicities compared with each other break spatial invariance Each $\exp(ipx)$, however, is linked with kinetic energy and momentum and so one cannot have a spatial distribution without a kinetic energy one. Thus a collection of $\exp(ipx)$ s creates an average kinetic energy which in turn is linked with a v_{rms} which may be mapped into Newton's continuous $x-t$ values. Physically, however, the $\exp(ipx)$ s are present as seen when one knocks

a particle out of a bound state. Thus it is the so-called quantum probability wave with its self-time and spatial resolution which creates the semblance of a particle in the quantum region. The idea of a particle in the particle wave duality seems to be a kind of mapping onto a continuous x-t space which only holds in certain cases i.e. there is no interaction affecting the wavelength. In the macroscopic world for which the wavelengths become tiny (nonmeasurable without extreme difficulty) the average x-t approach seems to be the only one observable. One may note that $\exp(ipx)$ with time removed is a mathematical-probabilistic approach as far as the repetition of wavelength units goes. This does not mean that nothing happens relative to external clocks and rules. It simply means that there is also an internal clock and ruler which are linked to interactions and cannot be ignored except in the macroscopic limit in which they cannot be measured easily.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Free Particle Action, Resolution and Invariance (preprint, zenodo, 2022)